

Experimental determination of diffusion coefficients of NaCl and KCl in *Haemonchus contortus* at 298.16 K

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The theory of diffusion and the modified diffusion cell apparatus developed earlier has now been employed to determine the diffusion coefficients of NaCl and KCl in *Haemonchus contortus* in the concentration range 0.0001–0.001 M at 298.16 K. The diffusion coefficient for both the salts first increases and then decreases with the increase in concentration. The results also establish the validity of the theory and diffusion coefficient can be determined experimentally for any similar type of parasitic nematode under *in vitro* conditions.

A survey of literature shows that diffusion processes in parasitic nematodes are not well understood although the basic principles of electrolyte and non-electrolyte diffusion in liquids have already been established¹. There are positive evidence regarding the transport of solute in nematodes^{2,3} but very little is known about the exact mechanism involved in the movement of the solute(s) through the body surface³. The role of the body-wall in nutrition of parasites is very complex⁴ and therefore a precise understanding of the transport processes will provide valuable information. Keeping this in view, we developed earlier a theory of diffusion, and designed and fabricated a diffusion cell apparatus⁵. In order to check the validity of the theory, the present work was carried out by taking *Haemonchus contortus* and integral diffusion coefficients of NaCl and KCl in the concentration range 0.0001–0.001 M were determined at 298.16 K.

Results and Discussion

The integral diffusion coefficient on rearrangement from equation (1) is

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{\beta_{\text{nematode}} t} \ln \frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_f}$$

Since β_{nematode} , time (t), ΔC_0 and ΔC_f are known from any single diffusion run using either NaCl or KCl, it is simple to determine \bar{D} . The \bar{D} values determined for both the salts are recorded in Table 1. The results reveal that the diffusion coefficient at 298.16 K, in general, increases upto 0.0004 M concentration, thereafter it continuously decreases upto 0.001 M. It is of interest to note that the \bar{D} values for the salts is maximum at the same concentration, viz. 0.0004 M, indicating that the physiological behaviour of the nematode at this concentration points towards maximum activity as far as the diffusion of the salts through the body-wall is concerned. The maximum values of \bar{D} at 0.0004 M for

Table 1. Integral diffusion coefficients (\bar{D} , cm² s⁻¹) of NaCl and KCl in *H. contortus* at 298.16 K

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	$\bar{D} \times 10^4$	
	NaCl	KCl
0.0001	0.400 ± 0.055	0.210 ± 0.005
0.0002	0.627 ± 0.067	0.770 ± 0.050
0.0003	1.153 ± 0.038	1 100 ± 0 098
0.0004	1.542 ± 0.059	1.700 ± 0.050
0.0005	1.460 ± 0.095	1.120 ± 0.032
0.0006	0.856 ± 0.024	1 020 ± 0.032
0.0007	0.617 ± 0.034	0 582 ± 0.042
0.0008	0.420 ± 0.006	0.396 ± 0.023
0.0009	0.365 ± 0.015	0.203 ± 0.037
0.0010	0.198 ± 0 049	0.067 ± 0.009

NaCl and KCl were found to be $1.542 \pm 0.059 \times 10^{-4}$ and $1.700 \pm 0.050 \times 10^{-4}$ cm² s⁻¹ respectively. The above study establishes the validity of the theory while the above experimental procedure can be employed with further modifications in the diffusion cell including stirring mechanism so that the diffusion coefficients can be determined more accurately.

Experimental

The modified glass diffusion cell⁶ (10 ml) was used. NaCl and KCl (AnalaR) were used and all solutions were prepared in conductivity water. An Elico CM-180 conductivity meter was used. An air-thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) was employed and all diffusion experiments were carried out without stirring the solution. It is, however, important to note that stagnant layers of the solution in the pores of the body-wall might affect somewhat the diffusion coefficients, and this can be minimized by ensuring homogeneity of the solution by stirring with a glass stirrer. The total volume of the

solution in the diffusion cell remained almost constant throughout. The total volume of extremely small bubbles found in the upper part of the cell due to the release of CO₂ during respiration of the nematode was so small that it may be considered negligible.

The adult and alive parasites *H. contortus* were obtained from abomassa of goats (*Capra hircus*) slaughtered at local abattoirs. Each diffusion experiment was performed with a single (female) nematode and three replications (using three diffusion cells) were carried out from a single lot in order to maintain constancy and reproducibility as far as possible. Since every time for new diffusion experiments nematodes were obtained from different goats, the overall results may still be in error by few percent because of the variation of the age and weight of the parasites. In spite of this, data obtained from *in vitro* studies concerning diffusion phenomena can be fruitfully employed for practical use.

Calibration of nematode : The nematode constant (β_{nematode}) is given by the equation,

$$\beta_{\text{nematode}} = \frac{A}{l} \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) = \frac{1}{D t} \ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_f} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{D} is the integral diffusion coefficient (cm² s⁻¹), t the time (s), ΔC_o and ΔC_f are the initial and final concentration differences between the solution and nematode respectively. The nematode calibration, therefore, requires a knowledge of the effective pore length (l) in the membrane of the nematode and the volume of nematode and the solution. The procedure to obtain the nematode constant from diffusional runs using very dilute solutions of KCl was discussed earlier⁵ and the final relation is

$$\beta_{\text{nematode}} \approx \frac{(\beta_{\text{nematode}})_{0.1 \text{ mM}}}{(\beta_{\text{nematode}})_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} = \frac{\left(\ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_o} \right)_{0.1 \text{ mM}}}{\left(\ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_o} \right)_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} \quad (2)$$

where the symbols have their usual significance.

In the present work, the procedure to determine β_{nematode} has been further improved because β_{nematode} from equation (2) will provide a ratio of two nematode constants and not a true constant as given by equation (1). The derivation of equation (2) in the original theory⁵ was necessary in order to obtain the condition $(\bar{D} t)_{0.1 \text{ mM KCl}} \approx (\bar{D} t)_{0.2 \text{ mM KCl}}$ since no data concerning diffusion coefficient of KCl or of any solute is presently available in any nematode. The above procedure⁵ to determine the nematode constant employing

equation (2) was, therefore, the only alternative. The new procedure employed in the present work is the same as discussed in the case of germinating seed and pollen grain^{6,7} (except that vacuum was not applied) where a single concentration of KCl (0.01 M) was employed, the diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}) of which in water at 25° is accurately known (1.939×10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹). In other words, β_{nematode} can be determined by performing a diffusion run using 0.01 M KCl at 25°, and also knowing t , the time (s) and ΔC_o and ΔC_f from the experiment it is simple to determine β_{nematode} from equation (1). In order to obtain constancy and reproducibility three replications were carried out by using the nematodes from the same goat. The values of β_{nematode} obtained at 25° were 0.9268, 0.8918 and 0.6976 giving an average of 0.8375. This average value was employed for determining the diffusion coefficients at different concentrations of NaCl and KCl. It is also important that the β_{nematode} obtained is from nematodes of a single goat and was not determined every time with nematodes obtained from different goats. This average value of β_{nematode} obtained from three replications is assumed to be nearly constant even if one determines β_{nematode} every time with new nematodes from different goats.

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